

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE MANAGEMENT IN THE BANKING INDUSTRY: A CONCEPTUAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The competition among organisations in the financial services sector is continuously increasing. The banking industry is the backbone of a nation's economy, and it is one of the largest industries in India in terms of revenue and employment. The banking structure played a major role in mobilising savings and promoting economic development. The intensity of the customer-organisation relationship has changed dramatically over time. Customer experience is the product of an interaction between an organisation and a customer over the duration of their relationship. Key elements like strategy, culture, processes, systems, etc. impact the CEM in banks. Antecedents like customer knowledge management, satisfaction, trust, and loyalty influence the CEM in organisations. This paper is an attempt to trace out the elements of CEM and the various factors leading to its neglect in the banking sector.

Keywords: Antecedents; Retail Banking; Customer Expectations; Social Environment; Service Encounter; Service Offering; Electronic Channels.

INTRODUCTION

The financial services industry (of which retail banking forms an integral part) is continuing its dynamic change. Dibb and Meadows (2001:169) argue that the major players in retail banking are becoming increasingly blurred as the effects of mergers, flotations, and new market entrants are felt. More than ever before, retail banking managers need a detailed understanding of their customers, their current and potential profitability, how to meet the needs of their best customers successfully by providing an appropriate range of financial services, and how to prevent these valuable customers from switching to other service providers. All of this must be done while keeping costs down and ensuring that business processes are streamlined and efficient. Retail banks are reshaping their businesses tactically and strategically to achieve stiff balance sheet and income statement goals. It is interesting to observe that these goals are achieved through traditional branch banking sales and service, focusing on existing customers (70–75% of sales) and setting behavioural standards for banking staff (Anat, 2006:1-2). However, there is a change in the air for retail banking. Retail banks all see competition increasing across the media, mail, and physical changes in branches. Retail banks see new forms and new names selling financial products. A retail bank has to have confidence in its strategies, the simplicity of its actions, and the speed of its implementation of change (Croxford et al., 2006:15). Retail banks differentiate themselves based on the effectiveness of their strategic decisions. Fundamental differentiators are more powerful than tactical differentiators, which have become more difficult to create and more difficult for competitors to compete against (Croxford et al., 2006:83). According to Croxford et al. (2006:84), "service and customer experiences are important differentiators" in retail banking. "The customer experience is a combination of everything you do, or fail to do, for that matter, that underpins any interaction with a customer or potential customer" (Shaw, 2005:5).

1. CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE MANAGEMENT

Customer Experience is the product of an interaction between an organisation and a customer over the duration of their relationship. This interaction is made up of three parts: the customer journey, the brand touch points the customer interacts with, and the environments the customer experiences (including the digital environment) during their experience. A good customer experience means that the individual's experience at all points of contact matches their expectations. Customer experience

implies customer involvement at different levels, such as rational, emotional, sensorial, physical, and spiritual. Customers respond diversely to direct and indirect contact with a company. Direct contact usually occurs when the purchase or use is initiated by the customer. Indirect contact often involves advertising, news reports, unplanned encounters with sales representatives, word-of-mouth recommendations, or criticisms. Customer experience encompasses every aspect of a company's offering—the quality of customer care, of course, but also advertising, packaging, product and service features, ease of use, and reliability. Creating direct relationships in the place where customers buy, use, and receive services by a business intended for customers, such as in-store or face-to-face contact with the customer, which could be seen through interacting with the customer through the retail staff, We then have indirect relationships, which can take the form of unexpected interactions through a company's product representative, certain services or brands, and positive recommendations, or they could even take the form of "criticism, advertising, news, reports' and many more along that line. The customer experience is created by the contributions of not only the customers' values but also the company providing the experience. Wharton's Professor of Marketing Barbara E. Kahn has established an evolutionary approach to customer experience as the third of four stages for any company in terms of its customer centricity maturity. These progressive phases are:

- **Product orientation:** Companies just manufacture goods and offer them in the best way.
- **Market orientation:** Some consideration of customer needs and segmentation arises, leading to the development of different marketing mix bundles for each one.
- **Customer experience:** Adding to the other two factors is some recognition of the importance of providing an emotionally positive experience to
- **Authenticity:** This is the top maturity stage for companies. Products and services emerge from the real soul of the brand and connect naturally and on a long-term, sustainable basis with clients and other stakeholders.

Kotler et al. (2013) say that customer experience is about "Adding value for customers buying products and services through customer participation and connection, by managing all aspects of the encounter". The encounter includes touch points. Businesses can create and modify touch points so that they are suited to their consumers, which changes or enhances the customers' experience. Creating an experience for the customer can lead to greater brand loyalty and brand recognition in the form of logos, colour, smell, touch, taste, etc. According to Bernd Schmitt, "the term customer Experience Management' represents the discipline, methodology, and/or process used to comprehensively manage a customer's cross-channel exposure, interaction, and transaction with a company, product, brand, or service." Adam Richardson says that a company must define and understand all dimensions of the customer experience in order to have long-Term success. The aim of CEM is to optimise the customer experience by gaining the loyalty of current customers in a multi-channel environment and ensuring they are completely satisfied. It's also to create advocates for their current customers among potential customers as a form of word-of-mouth marketing.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Rangarajan C. (2007), in his lecture, focuses on banking sector reforms and improvements in the performance of the Indian banking Industry. It is held that the development of the financial system is essential for sustaining higher economic growth. Reform measures were initiated in India so that banks could overcome external constraints and operate with greater flexibility. The favourable impact of banking sector reforms on the Indian banking Industry is also shown. Proper attention should be paid to issues like consolidation, capital adequacy, risk management, and customer service. Productivity and Profitability can be improved by combining corporate planning with organisational restructuring. Financial inclusion and governance have emerged as the key issues for socio-economic development. Verma Amitabh (2009) evaluated the impact of technology on the performance of Indian banks in terms of their profitability and productivity. IT has become a buzzword in the Indian banking industry. Technology can be the key differentiator between two banks and a major actor to attain a competitive

edge. The primary challenge for banks is to provide consistent service to customers, irrespective of the kind of channel they use. It was concluded that Indian Public sector banks have a unique advantage over their counterparts in terms of their branch network and large customer base, but it is the use of technology that will enable Public Sector Banks to build on their strengths. Schmitt (1999) says that companies can create experiential marketing by having customers sense, feel, think, act, and relate to a company and its brands. The experience concept has also redefined branding to include more than just logos, slogans, awareness, and images. The brand is about creating and delivering a specific, targeted experience associated with a product or service. Gerald Zaltman (2003) proposes that sub-conscious sensory and emotional elements derived from the total experience have a stronger influence on customer preference than the tangibles of a service. Almost 95 percent of the processing of the experience at touch points during interactions takes place at the unconscious level. He claims that the perception of experience happens at the subconscious level. Customers consciously and unconsciously filter a barrage of clues and organise them into a set of impressions. Some are rational, and some are emotional. Stephan H. Haeckel, Lewis P. Carbone, and Leonard L. Berry (2003) revealed that Customer experience management focuses different parts of an organisation on the common goal of creating an integrated and aligned customer experience. It provides a means for breaking down organisational barriers. They had identified three principles that would result in distinctive customer value through the customer experience. The three principles are as below:

Principle 1: Fuse experiential breadth and depth

Principle 2: Use Mechanics and Humanics to improve function

Principle 3: Connect Emotionally. Connecting emotionally with customers or managing customer emotions is not easily understood. Dikesh Kumar (2009) proposes that Customer Experience is a way to meet and exceed the expectations of the end customer through all channels of interaction. This leads to increased advocacy and referrals for the bank and, ultimately, profitable revenue growth. The customer continues to expect outstanding service, customised products, anytime-anywhere access to their money, and real-time updates and alerts of transactions across all channels. The benefits of a holistic, end-to-end approach to customer service result from managing customer relationships with real-time information and providing excellent customer experiences, leading to lifetime loyalty from the customer. But managing the customer experience across channels is not an easy job. It requires organisation-wide activity to bridge the various channels. Only then can customer interaction across channels be managed to result in an overall customer experience.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The Present study has been carried out to highlight the importance of customer experience management in banks. The study mainly attempts to identify and explain the elements of CEM and the factors behind its neglect in retail Banking.

4. DATA SOURCES AND METHODOLOGY

The study was of a descriptive nature and relied on secondary data sources. The information and conceptual base were extracted from existing research papers, Annual Reports of banks, and other relevant publications on the banking sector.

5. ELEMENTS OF CEM IN BANKS

From the definitions of customer experience management given above, it is clear that customer experience management consists of a variety of elements. The following key elements of customer experience management are entrenched across the organisation (Shaw, 2005: xix), namely strategy, culture, customer expectations, processes, channel approach, marketing and brand, systems, people, and measurement.

STRATEGY: The first important element of a total customer experience is strategy. Organisations require a strategy that creates a unified view of customers from the perspectives of operations, analytics, and collaboration along the entire customer relationship value chain (Heskett, 1997:106).

CULTURE: The second important element of a total customer experience is culture. Culture refers to the shared values, vision, or credo that creates a propensity for individuals to act in certain ways. According to Hrebiniak (2005:261), organisational culture includes the norms and values of the organisation, including the vision shared by its personnel. Culture usually has a behavioural component, defining the "way an organisation does things".

CUSTOMER EXPECTATIONS: The third important element of a total customer experience is customer expectations. The expectations of customers serve as a benchmark against which present and future service encounters can be compared. Customer expectations are what customers think they will receive from a service encounter. These expectations may be divided into at least three levels.

- The predicted service level (the anticipated level of performance)
- The desired service level (the level of service the customer wants or hopes to receive compared to the predicted service level)
- The adequate service level (the minimum level of service the customer will tolerate or accept without being dissatisfied (Cant et al., 2002:239).

Parasuraman, et al. (1990:34) state that customers evaluate an organisation's service quality by comparing service performance (perceptions) with what they think performance should be (expectations). Customers' service expectations provide a context for their assessment of the service. When service performance falls short of expectations a service quality gap results as depicted in the figure given below.

Figure 1: Service Quality Gap

A number of different attributes contribute to understanding customer expectations and customer loyalty, namely people, product and service delivery, place (convenience), product features, price, policies and procedures, and promotion and advertising (Smith, 2001:5). In this context, two primary components exist: physical and relational. Physical context is referred to as "mechanics clues" (sights, smells, sounds, and textures). Relational context is referred to as "humanic clues" (people's behaviours). Managing the customer experience means "orchestrating" all these "clues" to meet or exceed people's emotional needs and expectations. A successful service experience provider such as Disney spends many months training employees in relational methods so they can connect emotionally with guests during social interactions (Pullman & Gross, 2003:218).

PROCESSES: The fourth important element of a total customer experience is process. According to the Oxford dictionary, a process is "a series of actions or tasks performed in order to do, make, or achieve something" (Hornby, 1998:922). Process has been identified as one of the additional elements in the marketing mix. Once organisations have a shared view of customer experience, processes are needed to reinforce and support the goal of improving customer experience (Dorsey & Bodine, 2006:7).

MARKETING AND BRAND: The sixth important element of a total customer experience is marketing and the brand. Marketing is defined as "a social process by which individuals and groups obtain what they need and want through creating and exchanging products and value with others" (Kotler, 1984:4). More recently, Hair, Bush, and Ortinau (2006:5) state that marketing's purpose is to enable an organisation to plan and implement "pricing, promotion, and distribution of products, services, and ideas to create satisfaction. According to Aaker and Keller (1990:29), an important brand association is the overall brand attitude. Brand attitude is based on certain attributes such as durability, incidence of defects, serviceability, features, and performance. Attitude is conceptualised in terms of the customer's perception of the overall quality of the brand. An organisation's first step in managing the total customer experience is recognising the clues it is sending to customers. The clues that make up a customer experience are everywhere and easily discernible. Anything that can be perceived, sensed, or recognised by its absence is an experience clue. Thus, the product or service provides one set of clues, the physical setting offers more clues, and the employees—through their gestures, comments, dress, and tone of voice—provide still more clues (Berry, Carbone, & Haeckel, 2002:85–86). "A strong brand promise can influence what customers remember about their experiences with a product or service" (Barlow & Steward, 2004:42). Barlow and Steward (2004:45) also believe that a brand idea can be enforced by means of pictures, language, and behaviour, all of which evoke emotions. Human behaviour is the primary means of brand reinforcement within the realm of customer service. "Branding should be the differentiating mechanism, separating an organization's products and services from those of its competitors" (Kumar, 2004:148). It is the brand that shapes the customer experience. Customers come to a brand with a set of assumptions about that brand. The brand and the customer experience should correspond (Shaw 2005:137).

SYSTEMS: The seventh element of a total customer experience is systems. Systems are designed and managed in organisations through information technology (IT). IT enables modern organisations to integrate their supply, production, and delivery processes so that operations are triggered by customer orders, not by production plans that push products and services through the value chain. An integrated system, from customer orders upstream to raw material suppliers, enables all the organisational units along the value chain to realise enormous improvements in cost, quality, and response time (Kaplan & Norton, 1996:4).

PEOPLE: People are the eighth important element of a total customer experience. People are one of the 7 Ps of the marketing mix, also referred to as personnel or employees, and represent the "key battleground for many organisations" (Ind, 2001:67–72). An organisation in Stockholm (India, 2001:67–72) defined the 4Fs to steer its employees: fun, fame, fortune, and future. The 4Fs were designed to influence how people behaved internally and how they interacted with customers.

6. Why was CEM ignored?

CEOs may not actively deny the significance of customer experience or, for that matter, the tools used to collect, quantify, and analyse it, but many don't adequately appreciate what those tools can reveal. Three forces conspire to preserve this gap.

TOO MUCH MONEY ALREADY LAVISHED ON CRM

Having spent millions of dollars on customer relationship management software, many CEOs consider their problem to be not a lack of customer information but a superfluity of it. Before investing more time and money, executives justifiably want to know how customer experience data is different and what its value is.

To put it starkly, the difference is that CRM captures what a company knows about a particular customer—his or her history of service requests, product returns, and inquiries, among other things—whereas customer experience data captures customers' subjective thoughts about a particular

company. The CRM tracks customer actions after the fact; CEM (customer experience management) captures the immediate response of the customer to its encounters with the company. Employees accustomed to reading the marketing department’s dry analyses of CRM point-of-sale data easily grasp the distinction upon hearing a frustrated customer’s very words. (For a detailed account of the difference between the two approaches, see exhibit 1, "CEM Versus CRM.")

Exhibit 1: CEM Vs CRM

	What	When	How Monitored	Who Uses the Information	Relevance to Future Performance
Customer Experience Management (CEM)	Captures and distributes what a customer thinks about a company	At points of customer interaction ‘touch points’	Surveys, targeted studies, observational studies, “voice of customer” research	Businesses or functional leaders, in order to create fulfillable expectations and better experiences with products and services	Leading: Locates places to add offerings in the gaps between expectations and experience.
Customer Relationship Management (CRM)	Captures and distributes what a company knows about a customer	After there is a record of a customer interaction	Point-of-sales data, market research, Web site click-through, automated tracking of sales	Customer-facing groups such as sales, marketing, field service, and customer service, in order to drive more efficient and effective execution.	Lagging: Drives cross selling by bundling products in demand with ones that aren’t

Moreover, many CEOs don’t sufficiently appreciate the distinction between customer satisfaction, which they believe they have heavily documented, and customer experience, which always demands further investigation.

LACK OF ATTUNEMENT TO CUSTOMERS’ NEEDS

Leaders who rose through customer-facing functions, such as Cisco Systems CEO John Chambers, are more likely to act with reference to customer experience than those who have not. When competing new technologies are difficult to choose among, Cisco defers its choice until key customers have registered their reactions. Because the company knows there will be a market for the choice it finally makes, it can afford to commit itself later than its competitors. In contrast, executives who rose through finance, engineering, or manufacturing often regard managing the customer experience as the responsibility of sales, marketing, or customer service.

FEAR OF WHAT THE DATA MAY REVEAL

It’s easy to say one’s business is customer-driven when there is no data to prove otherwise. Once data starts flowing, the bogeymen come out of the closet. Can we afford to do what customers are asking for? How do we choose between conflicting preferences? Can we accept what customers say they are experiencing without first telling them what they should be experiencing? Corporate leaders, who

would never tolerate a large gap between forecasted and actual revenues, prefer to look the other way when company and customer assessments diverge, as they do in the Bain survey. Executives also hesitate to act on findings because experience data is more ambiguous than customers' actions—the orders they place, for instance. However, statistical analysis has developed to the point where it can dependably quantify both the relative importance of each touch point and the experience it provides. It can also isolate key transactions, accounts, regions, customer segments, and so forth, and then parse the resulting data. About ten years ago, companies started collecting experience information electronically. Now they can instantly combine it with data collected from CRM systems and other customer databases, conduct analyses of both individual and aggregate responses in real time, and then automatically route and track issues needing resolution.

ALL HANDS ON BOARD

Many organisations place responsibility for collecting and assessing customer experience data within a single, IT-supported customer-facing group. Doing so accomplishes at least three things: It saves money; it protects customers from redundant and annoying solicitations; and it permits direct comparison of customers on the basis of their location, choice of product, or some other criterion. But it is a mistake to assign to customer-facing groups overall accountability for the design, delivery, and creation of a superior customer experience, thereby excluding those more distant from the customer from understanding it. In contrast to this common pattern, Palm drew on customer experience to make the Treo one of its most successful products ever. A combination of cell phone and Palm Pilot, the original Treo used the same built-in rechargeable battery as the Palm organisers. When used as a cell phone, the device consumed far more power than it did when used as an organiser. So customers who were heavy users of the cell phone feature found that their Treos were often losing power—and often at an inconvenient distance from their rechargers. Complaints about this problem began showing up in Palm's customer-service transaction surveys. But the customer service department could offer the Treo's unhappy owners only minor power-saving tips. Dissatisfied with the status quo, customer service vice president Dan Gilbert, showing unusual initiative, distributed the experience data his department had collected to product development, which went to work on the problem.

OBTAINING THE RIGHT INFORMATION

There are three patterns of customer experience information, each with its own pace and level of data collection. (For a detailed breakdown of the three patterns, see exhibit 2, "Tracking Customer Experience: Persistent, Periodic, Pulsed.")

Exhibit -2 Patterns of Customer Experience Management

Pattern and Purpose	Owner	Data Collection Frequency and Scope	Collection and Analysis Methodology	Discussion and Action Forums
Past Patterns: Captures a recent experience. Intended to improve transactional experiences Tracks experience goals and trends Assesses impact of new initiatives Identifies emerging issues	Central group or functions	Persistent: Electronic surveys linked to high-volume transactions or an ongoing feedback system Automatically triggered by the completion of a transaction Focused, short-	Web based, in-person, or phone surveys User forums and blogs	Analysed within functions, central, survey groups, or both Cross-functional issues directed to general managers Strategic analysis and actions directed

		cycle, timed data collection Feedback, volunteered by users in online forums		by general managers
Present Pattern: Tracks current relationships and experience issues with an eye toward identifying future opportunities. Keeps a consistent yet deeper watch on state of relationship and other factors Looks forward as well as backward Used with more critical populations and issues	Central group, business units or functions	Periodic: Quarterly account reviews Relationships studies User experience studies User-group polling	Web-based surveys preceded by preparation in person Direct contact in person or by phone Moderated user forums Focus groups and other regularly scheduled formats	Initial analysis by sponsoring group Broader trends and issues forwarded to general managers' strategic and operating forums Deeper analysis of emerging issues at the corporate, business unit, or local level
Potential Patterns: Targets inquiries to unveil and test future opportunities.	General management or functions	Pulsed: One-off, special purpose driven Interim readings of trends	Driven by specific customers or unique problems Very focused Incorporates existing knowledge of customer relationship	Centered within sponsoring group with coordination by and support from central group

TRACKING CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE: Persistent, Periodic, Pulsed Companies can monitor various patterns of interaction with customers to gain a better understanding of the customer experience they are providing. Depending on the precise information a company is seeking, it may choose to analyse past patterns, present patterns, potential patterns, or a combination. Each pattern requires a distinct method of generating and analysing data and will yield different types of insights.

Analyses of present patterns are not simply evaluations of the meaning and success of a recent encounter. They envision a continuing relationship with the customer. Consequently, questions may extend to the customer's awareness of alternative suppliers, new features the customer might desire, and what it sees as challenges to its competitiveness. Given the broad scope of the inquiry, this type of monitoring shouldn't be triggered solely by a customer initiated transaction. Instead, information on a company's key products and services should be gathered at scheduled intervals, or "periodically."

Hewlett-Packard and the consulting firm BearingPoint, for example, approach every key customer annually. By initiating contact with different customers at different times throughout the year, BearingPoint has created an almost persistent data flow that does not depend on. On the completion of a given transaction, while permitting comparisons among customers on a range of issues. BearingPoint learned in this fashion that the best practises it had established in one vertical-market group had not migrated to other groups. Potential patterns are uncovered by probing for opportunities, which often emerge from the interpretation of customer data as well as the observation of customer behaviour. Like the study Gilead conducted, such probes are outgrowths of strategies usually involving the targeting of particular customer segments and are therefore unscheduled, or "pulsed." The findings are often used to inform the product development process. Most companies apply a single summary metric to data on past and present patterns. The customer experience metric Net Promoter, for example, registers customers' experiences in aggregate—that is, their positive ones minus their negative ones. Intuit's founder, Scott Cook, uses Net Promoter Scores for goal setting and engaging the organisation's attention, though he recognises that a rising or falling score doesn't begin to reveal what is driving the trend. As relationships with customers deepen, companies tend to collect data with greater frequency. The patterns that emerge suggest further areas of inquiry. For example, present relationship studies may indicate that on-site service experience is lacking. After improvements are made, it's common to use a transaction survey following each service call to assess progress. A subsequent, more comprehensive survey may show good experience with service response time but low overall ratings, triggering a special study to identify customers' priorities among a range of service experience factors. Low cost and ease of modification make surveys the overwhelming favourite for measuring past and present patterns. E-mail-based surveys are superior to paper-based ones because they can be more easily shared; they allow rapid distribution; they give the surveyor the flexibility to extend or abbreviate the questioning according to the wishes of the respondent or the substance of the response; they minimise delays in analysing the results; and they lead to quick action, such as a referral to a general manager should scores fall below a predetermined level. E-mail surveys can also be more easily tailored. A well-designed survey is not simply one that elicits the desired information. It must itself avoid becoming an unfortunate aspect of the customer experience. Hence, it shouldn't be onerous for the taker or deny him the chance to communicate the special nature of his experience. One way of keeping surveys mercifully brief is to avoid asking about matters like recent purchases that the company already has a record of. Nor should they be triggered by the transactions of regular customers, such as purchasing agents. Such customers are, after all, among those a business can least afford to annoy. By the same token, corporate sanctions imposed on dealers who receive low scores shouldn't be so harsh that retailers try to discourage customers from responding by offering to fix any problem on the spot. The individual customer may be placated, but widespread resort to this practise keeps general management from obtaining a broad picture of systemic problems.

7. CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE IN RETAIL BANKING

According to Grewal et al. (2009), the customer experience includes every point of contact at which the customer interacts with the business. In retail banking, these points of contact are the bank branch, automated teller machines (ATMs), telephone banking, cellphone banking, and internet banking. The branch experience, ATM experience, internet banking experience, telephone banking experience, and cellphone banking experience, as well as service delivery and service quality

All these shape customer experiences and behaviours. Backstrom and Johansson (2006) argue that branch experiences are to a large extent constituted by the behaviour of the bank's staff, service offerings, and the layout and design of the facilities. The friendliness of the bank personnel, their competence and knowledge about the products and services offered, as well as a pleasant and welcoming branch environment, can lead to an enhanced customer experience. If the bank employees are polite, responsive, and knowledgeable, strong relationships can be formed between the bank and its customers. These relationships tend to lead to satisfied, committed, and loyal customers. The branch

layout and design have a significant impact on the customer experience. Ng (2002) finds that the physical features of the retail outlet, such as the layout and background music, influence customers' experiences and satisfy their psychological needs for social interaction, comfort, and sensory stimulation. The design of the retail bank branch has become critical to the success of the business. Capitalising on the branch's design and layout by creating an open and welcoming environment conducive to building customer relationships has become very important.

The advent of internet banking, the proliferation of ATMs, and telephone and cellphone banking have provided alternative service distribution channels to traditional branch banking. These alternative methods of banking offer customers flexibility, convenience, and 24 hour access to banking services. The efficiency and seamless delivery of services through these channels impact the customer experience. According to Calisir and Gumussoy (2008), the development of alternative banking service delivery channels is key to retaining existing customers as well as attracting new ones. Banks generate revenues by charging fees for services such as credit, transactions, savings, and investment accounts. The prices and quality of services, distribution technologies, and volumes of customers served are the major elements of competition in the industry. The fees charged by banks influence the consumer's decisions and are a major consideration in the choice of a bank. Van Heerden and van der Westhuizen (2008) find that retail banking customers have experienced relatively large increases in bank service fees over the last ten years. Retail banks offer customers a variety of products and services. These offerings can be classified under three primary activities: taking deposits, issuing loans, and investing in securities (Kablan, 2009). Due to increased competition among banks and non-bank financial services, these products and services have become commoditized (Devlin & Gerrard, 2004; Haenlein, Kaplan, & Beeser, 2007). New innovations and products are easy to replicate, and differentiating solely on the basis of product offerings and price in the marketplace no longer gives a competitive advantage. Retail banking consumers have evolved; they have become more sophisticated and demanding (Arbore & Busacca, 2009). These consumers demand a wide range of suitable banking products and services. They differ in their sensitivity to price, preference for distribution technology, and average distance from the retail bank. Retail banking consumers evaluate financial products on price, convenience, and quality (Byers & Lederer, 2001). Their changing behaviour and attitudes make it easy for them to switch banks if they are dissatisfied. As a result, consumer switching has become a major concern throughout the financial services sector, particularly in the mortgage market (Dougan, 2004). Customer complaints are often accompanied by a rise in the number of customers who switch to other service providers.

THE ANTECEDENTS OF CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE

The impact of the following antecedents of customer experience in the retail banking environment can be identified.

Social Environment: Research has shown that the consumer's perceptions about the product or service can be influenced by the people and groups they associate with White and Dahl (2007) demonstrate that the desire to avoid certain groups of people can influence consumer evaluations and choices. To emphasise the influence of the social environment on the consumer's preference and choice, Berger and Heath (2007) argue that people often diverge from their internal drives to ensure that others make desired identity inferences about them. The need to identify with others and conform to their expectations contributes to the consumer's decision-making process within a social setting. Wooten and Reed II (2004) argue that people who value approval but lack confidence in their abilities to discern or enact desired impressions often protect themselves from losses of approval by avoiding undesired, contestable, or even noticeable impressions.

Service Encounter (Interaction): Service encounters involve social interaction between the customer and the service provider. For the service provider, such an encounter represents a moment of truth. According to Czepiel (1990), the success of a business depends on the functional and social performance of the service provider's interactions with the customer.

Over time, service encounters can develop into a close social relationship, which ultimately leads to psychological loyalty between the customer and the service provider. Reynolds and Beatty (1999) examine the nature of a relationship between a consumer and a service provider and the role that relationship plays in enhancing the service experience.

Atmosphere: The spending behaviour of the consumer can be significantly influenced by the store atmosphere (Kamaladevi, 2010). Store atmospheres are increasingly considered a means of creating a pleasurable consumption experience for the consumer. The nicer retail environments and prestigious ambience can lead to an increase in the perceived level of credibility towards a service provider and, subsequently, a higher likelihood to purchase. Baker, Parasuraman, Grewal, and Voss (2002) argue that the store's environmental dimensions (design, social, and ambient) influence consumers' perceptions of store choice. These perceptions refer to inferences about the levels of quality, price, and value that consumers would expect in a store on the basis of store environment cues. Bitner (1992) states that the physical setting can be used as a way in which customers can be attracted to and/or satisfied by a firm's services. He demonstrates how the physical setting of a service firm can aid or hinder the accomplishment of both internal organisational goals and external marketing goals.

Service Offering: Services are designed to meet the customer's needs by appropriately integrating the company's investments in physical assets, processes, people skills, and materials. Kamaladevi (2010) defines customer service as the ability of an organisation to constantly and consistently give customers what they want and need. Hume et al. (2006) argue that the service experience is created through a series of encounters and interactions between the provider and the consumer and that the extent to which these encounters are consistent with the customers' wants and needs relates to the value, customer satisfaction, and quality of service.

Price (Cost structure): The consumer's perception of the price, quality, and value of an offering plays a significant role in influencing shopping behaviour and product choice. Zeithaml (1988) defines price from a consumer's perspective as that which is given up or sacrificed to obtain a product. For the seller, a price captures the value created and earns revenue. According to Grewal et al. (2009), if the price of a product or service is too high, consumers may view it as poor value for money and not buy it. On the other hand, if the price is set too low, consumers may perceive the product or service to be of poor quality, standard, or other negative attributes and may not buy it either. Rao and Monroe (1989) suggest that for consumer products, there is a significant correlation between price and the perceived quality and value of an offering.

Brand: Brands and branding play an important role in the organisation, and an increasing number of firms recognise brands as their most valuable assets. According to Kimpakorn and Tocquer (2007), the concept of brand has its roots in the consumer field and is often defined from a customer's perspective. Kimpakorn and Tocquer (2007) define a brand as a collection of associations in the mind of a customer that are connected to a brand or a symbol. Brand equity, therefore, is determined by the value, uniqueness, and power of these associations.

Electronic Channels (ATMs, Internet banking, etc.): The advances in telecommunication, information technology, and online technology and security have brought about new opportunities and possibilities for both sellers and buyers of goods and services. Online retailing, as a way of doing business, enables retailers to attract consumers who demand efficient use of their time and are less interested in traditional retailing. From the consumer's perspective, online retailing offers convenience and transcends the limitations of time and space.

Past Customer Experience: The consumer's past experiences and interactions with a retailer or service provider create an image and perception that influence their attitudes and behaviours towards the store. According to Osman (2001), the customer's perception and attitude towards the store may be a result of the consumer's evaluation of the perceived important aspects of the store, moulded and remoulded by his or her direct experiences with the store's overall milieu. Woodruff, Cadotte, and Jenkins (1983) point out that a consumer's beliefs about the brand are derived from personal use

experience and that the nature and amount of a consumer's experience with an evoked set of brands are important determinants of the satisfaction process.

8. CONCLUSION

Financial services firms across the world are striving to improve their business processes by liaising with customers to survive and compete successfully. In today's highly competitive environment, managing relationships with customers and ensuring customer delight has become a necessity. Customer loyalty is crucial for both organisations and customers. Customer experience is the product of an interaction between an organisation and a customer over the duration of their relationship. The key elements involved in customer experience management include strategy, culture, expectations, processes, marketing and brand, systems, and people. The CEM was neglected in the organisations due to too much money already spent on CRM, a lack of attunement to customers' needs, a fear of revealing data, etc. The customer experience in retail banking is mainly impacted by the social environment, service encounter, service offering, brand, and past customer experience. Banks willing to improve their relationships with customers need constant monitoring of the customer experience. The managers need to establish some benchmarks that should be used as the basis for comparison with major competitors. Customer knowledge management, satisfaction, trust, and loyalty play a key role in the overall process of customer experience management.

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